

Distribution Concept FDM:Storage.nrw

Guidance and information on the allocation of DataStorage.nrw and DataArchive.nrw storage space by the RDM State Basic Services of DH.NRW

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Introduction

This document sets out the management guidelines for the research data storage infrastructure in North Rhine-Westphalia (FDM:Storage.nrw), which currently comprises DataStorage.nrw and DataArchive.nrw.

The management of FDM:Storage.nrw is led and coordinated by the **FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management Team** at RWTH Aachen University. The governance of this management is integrated into the structure of Coscine.nrw². Part of the governance structure is the **advisory board**, which comprises representatives of DH.NRW users and the spokesperson for the FDM:Storage.nrw Operating Committee. The Operating Committee is the operational governance body, comprising all participating institutions of the FDM:Storage.nrw Consortium³.

DataStorage.nrw is a redundant S3 object storage system operated at four DH.NRW university sites: the University of Duisburg-Essen, the University of Paderborn, the University of Cologne and RWTH Aachen University. As part of FDM:Storage.nrw, DataStorage.nrw supports the implementation of the DH.NRW's⁴ state-level RDM concept. The object storage system was designed for particularly large volumes of data requiring long-term retention and offers a capacity of up to 24 petabytes.

DataArchive.nrw is another storage platform scheduled to be established in 2026. It is specifically designed for 'cold data', i.e. data that users access only rarely. To enable an economically and environmentally sustainable solution for storing even large volumes of data over extended periods, this platform utilises tape storage technology. Storage takes place at two universities (RWTH Aachen University, University of Cologne) to achieve the highest possible data persistence through geographical distribution and duplicate data storage, ensuring that the stored data remains reliably available over a long period without loss.

FDM:Storage.nrw is accessed and used via services offered as RDM State Basic Services⁵ (e.g. repositories, cloud services) by DH.NRW universities for collaborative use by other DH.NRW universities (see also the chapter 'Cooperative Use').

Recipients

This document sets out the conditions under which an RDM State Basic Service operated by DH.NRW may deposit datasets into FDM:Storage.nrw. It is therefore intended for IT service providers who operate such an RDM State Basic Service. The allocation guidelines were drawn up by the FDM:Storage.nrw service management team and approved by the advisory board.

In addition to RDM State Basic Services, this management concept is also aimed at large-scale research projects at universities within the DH.NRW. Large-scale research projects are research infrastructures that open up unique research opportunities and make these available to a broad group of researchers. Examples include telescopes and particle accelerators. Such research infrastructures usually have the funding to ensure the management of the data generated. Direct

² See <https://about.coscine.de/> (accessed on 07.05.2026)

³ See <https://www.fdm.nrw/fdm-storage-nrw> (accessed on 07.05.2026)

⁴ DH.NRW I AG FDM. (2024). Digitales Ökosystem DH.NRW - Landeskonzept FDM. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11242683>

⁵ See <https://www.fdm.nrw/technische-fdm-landesdienste> (accessed on 07.05.2026)

use of FDM:Storage.nrw by large-scale research projects must be applied for at an early stage at RWTH Aachen University and must follow the guidelines set out here. An assessment will be made as to whether a contribution towards costs is required. Indirect use of FDM:Storage.nrw via already connected RDM State Basic Services is only permitted if the respective selection criteria of the RDM State Basic Service (so-called selection policies) are also met.

Governance

Important decisions regarding the management of FDM:Storage.nrw are taken by FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management on the recommendation of the advisory Board.

For this purpose, the FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management draws up a decision paper in which the subject of the decision is explained, the interests and positions of the parties involved are outlined, and a reasoned proposal for a decision is put forward. Decision papers may be initiated or drawn up by both State Basic Services and the FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management itself.

Decision drafts are made available to the Advisory Board no later than 7 calendar days before its next meeting. The Advisory Board issues its recommendation for a decision. In doing so, it is free to endorse a decision option already set out in the draft or to propose a decision option of its own. It may provide reasons for its recommendation but is not obliged to do so.

Key decisions to which this process applies include the accreditation of a RDM State Basic Service or a major research project, the withdrawal of accreditation, and the confirmation of data recovery. It is also applied to other issues of sufficient significance that cannot currently be foreseen. The FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management determines whether an issue is of sufficient significance.

Definitions

RDM State Basic Services are applications developed in accordance with the RDM regional strategy that make storage resources from FDM:Storage.nrw available to end users.

For the purposes of this document, **research data** refers to digital data that has been collected, generated or used as part of a research initiative.

The **research data storage infrastructure of DH.NRW (FDM:Storage.nrw)** currently consists of DataStorage.nrw and, in future, will also include DataArchive.nrw.

The **FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management** consists of at least two people (one lead manager and one deputy) who work as RDM staff at the IT Centre of RWTH Aachen University. RWTH Aachen University is the lead institution in the FDM:Storage.nrw consortium.

A **selection policy** for RDM State Basic Service is a guideline that describes the selection criteria, specifying which types of files are to be included in and managed by the service, and which criteria must be considered. This guideline helps to ensure the quality and relevance of the stored data.

Objectives and values of FDM:Storage.nrw

FDM:Storage.nrw serves as a capacity and persistence layer for the storage of research data. Storage can be guaranteed for a maximum of 10 years following the conclusion of the research

initiative in which the data was generated. DataStorage.nrw offers an accessible way to store data sustainably at an early stage of research data lifecycle, ideally immediately after it has been collected.

FDM:Storage.nrw is intended exclusively for research data and is open to research data from all academic disciplines. FDM:Storage.nrw is committed to Good Scientific Practice (GSP)⁶ and the FAIR principles. Data stored there must be structured, annotated with sufficient metadata, documented and referenced by persistent identifiers (PIDs) to ensure its reusability. This is ensured by the applications through which the storage space is provided and by the review of storage space applications or publication requests.

FDM:Storage.nrw establishes the infrastructural framework (GSP, Guideline 3) that enables the management of research data in accordance with the FAIR principles (GSP, Guideline 13) and safeguards research results against manipulation (GSP, Guideline 12).

FDM:Storage.nrw is obliged to maintain transparency. Statistical information on usage is made publicly available. The allocation of storage space must also be carried out in accordance with transparent, non-discriminatory procedures.

General conditions

The RDM State Basic Services of DH.NRW enter contracts with the storage consortium's operating committee for the use of FDM:Storage.nrw and undergo an accreditation process based on the management concept outlined here. Each RDM State Basic Service designates two contact people to the FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management.

The target group for RDM State Basic Services are researchers from participating universities. Participating universities must first enter into the relevant agreements with the respective RDM State Basic Service. All member universities of DH.NRW that are state-funded or state-refinanced are eligible to participate.⁷ FDM:Storage.nrw can also be utilised via regional RDM State Basic Services to support researchers through NFDI consortia based at participating universities.

Science-led Procurement Process

The technical provision and management of storage space on FDM:Storage.nrw must be carried out in accordance with standardized, science-led procedures. These procedures must be identical for researchers at all participating universities and must include

- the application for storage resources per research initiative,
- the assessment of applications through a science-led process
- the provisioning of storage resources.

⁶ Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft. (2022). Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice. Code of Conduct. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3923601>

⁷ At this time, this excludes only Witten-Herdecke University as a purely privately funded institution of higher education.

For each research project, up to 100 GB can be allocated to researchers by RDM State Basic Services without the need for further application, if compliance with the FAIR principles is technically ensured by the RDM State Basic Service in accordance with the concept set out in the relevant accreditation. The provision of up to 100 GB of storage space without the need for an application promotes user-friendliness and flexibility by enabling users to access resources quickly and easily. This facilitates the implementation of small projects and ensures that the administrative burden is proportionate to the storage requirements. The 100 GB limit is based on several years of experience within the RDS.nrw context. A change to the automatic allocation of storage space may be made upon application by a State Basic Service through the FDM:Storage.nrw decision-making process.

Any additional storage requirements must be applied for and reviewed by at least two members of a panel of experts from the participating institutions to ensure compliance with the FAIR principles and good data organization. In addition, the reviewers must ensure that the application meets the criteria for the formats research project, data publication or data pool (see the chapter on [research initiatives](#)). At least one external reviewer from the RDM context of another participating institution must be involved. Alternatively, the review may be carried out by trained staff from the relevant RDM State Basic Service, provided that this service conducts quality assurance and assumes responsibility for the data. Suitable reviewers are distinguished by relevant professional experience in the field of RDM or appropriate further training.

For storage requirements exceeding 125 TB, a scientific justification for the high storage requirements must also be provided by suitable external independent scientific reviewers (see Jansen et al. 2025⁸). Scientific experts must be active researchers in the field of the proposed project. The scientific review may be replaced with reference to an application that has already undergone a scientific peer review, including an assessment of data management plans (e.g. DFG), provided that the storage space requirement is clear from this.

Possible storage period

FDM:Storage.nrw offers pure bitstream preservation (further details can be found in the operational concept). Storage can be guaranteed for a maximum of 10 years following the end of the research initiative in which the data was generated. The providers of RDM State Basic Services, through which storage space is made available, assume technical responsibility for the data and maintain, for the duration of storage, the link to the context of origin, the responsible persons and the descriptive metadata, even across necessary data migrations. The RDM State Basic Services ensure, through an appropriate process, that orphaned data is deleted. This process must be submitted as part of the accreditation process.

The FDM:Storage.nrw requires periodic updates and, where necessary, expansions. The commitment regarding the duration of storage by the universities of the DataStorage.nrw consortium (University of Duisburg-Essen, University of Paderborn, University of Cologne and RWTH Aachen University) and DataArchive.nrw (RWTH Aachen University, University of Cologne) is therefore subject to further funding from the State of North Rhine-Westphalia. In the event of a loss of state

⁸ Jansen, K., Lang, I., Grünwald, K. M. E., Bossert, L. C., Poltze, M., Koch, K., Schick, E., Schramm, A., Werger, M., & Nellesen, M. (2025). Begutachtungsleitlinien für Coscine DataStorage.nrw-Ressourcen - Handreichung und Erläuterung zur Begutachtung eingereicherter Speicherplatzanträge. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16035496>

funding, the technical process for the associated decommissioning is set out in the FDM:Storage.nrw operational concept. FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management will be informed by the operating committee of the decommissioning at the time the decision is made and will pass this information directly on to the designated contact persons of the respective state-level services.

Supported research initiatives

The RDM State Basic Services may only allocate storage space on FDM:Storage.nrw within the framework of defined research initiatives: these include research projects, data pools, data recovery and data publications. Accordingly, storage space may not be allocated to individual researchers, institutes or core facilities without a link to a specific research initiative. All research initiatives for which a RDM State Basic Service allocates storage space on FDM:Storage.nrw must have the following characteristics:

- **Timeframe:** The start date of an initiative is clearly specified in the relevant metadata.
- **Data:** The data collected by an initiative are clearly related in terms of content. This must be reflected in standardized metadata for research initiatives. The conditions and requirements for contributing data are defined. Quality assurance processes are defined and implemented.
- **Participants:** Initiatives are carried out by a defined group of people, the composition of which may change over time. There are one or more lead individuals (Principal Investigator, PI), who usually remain the same throughout the project duration. Individuals who are primarily responsible for applying for and using storage space on FDM:Storage.nrw must be employed at a participating university or have a direct affiliation with an NFDI consortium based at a participating university.
- **Organizational affiliation:** A research initiative is based at one or more research institutions. Where several institutions are involved, one of them acts as the lead partner and must be primarily associated with the initiative.

These features enable research data to be managed in accordance with the research data lifecycle. Research data from research initiatives that are already being preserved for the long term elsewhere by a recognized organization should not be duplicated on FDM:Storage.nrw. This should be considered during the science-led procurement process conducted by the RDM State Basic Service.

Research projects

The primary purpose of FDM:Storage.nrw is to provide research projects with the necessary storage space to safeguard the research data generated or used in the project for the duration of the project and for up to 10 years after its completion.

Research projects (in addition to those listed under Research Initiatives) have the following characteristics:

- **Timeframe:** A research project is of limited duration. The end date of the project is clearly specified in the associated metadata. Any subsequent changes to the project duration must be registered by the RDM State Basic Service.

Data pools

Data pools are often long-term collections (i.e. usually with no defined end date) of data that are thematically related, which have been generated or collected in different contexts and are reused in different contexts. The thematic connection between the data is also reflected in metadata fields that are common to all stored data. For storage on FDM:Storage.nrw, the following characteristics are relevant (in addition to those listed under research initiatives):

- **Timeframe:** Both the collection and the subsequent use of the data may be of indefinite duration or have defined end dates. Therefore, applications for data pools are initially approved for a collection phase of up to five years and a subsequent utilization phase of a further five years. At the end of the collection and/or utilization phase, an extension of a further three years may be applied for. Applications for extension may be submitted repeatedly without limit. In the case of extension applications, the respective RDM State Basic Services will also assess whether the criteria set out in the concept have been met.
- **Storage requirements overtime:** A storage space application must be submitted for each collection phase. The expected storage space requirement must always be specified for the end of each year within the collection phases.
- **Usage:** Data pools have a detailed usage concept setting out the intended subsequent use. The usage concept defines the group of people authorized to make subsequent use of the data. If there are any preconditions for subsequent use by external parties, these must also be set out. The usage concept describes all relevant legal requirements that must be complied with for subsequent use. In addition, it sets out the technical requirements necessary for subsequent use and how these are ensured and continuously monitored. The creation, implementation and submission of the usage concept are defined in the Selection Policy of the respective state basic services.
- **Contributors:** The groups of participants consisting of contributing and secondary-use researchers are defined in the concepts mentioned above. Researchers applying to use the data pool must demonstrate that they possess sufficient expertise and resources to maintain the data pool. A lead researcher and at least one deputy lead researcher must be appointed. These individuals should hold permanent positions at their respective organizations.

Data recovery

In the event of data recovery involving datasets of exceptional scientific value for which no other suitable storage location is available in the short term, the criteria for the aforementioned types of research initiatives may be temporarily waived. Upon submission of a respective application, the relevant Service Management Team of the RDM State Basic Service will contact the FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management. The FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management will assess whether the situation constitutes data recovery and allocates the appropriate storage space. The decision regarding long-term storage on FDM:Storage.nrw will be made in accordance with the FDM:Storage.nrw decision-making process.

Data publication

A data publication is the formal release of a research dataset in a trusted repository, ensuring that the dataset is discoverable, citable, accessible and reusable in accordance with

the FAIR principles. This includes standardized metadata, a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI) and defined usage rights/licenses. Data Publications have the following characteristics:

- **Timeframe:** A data publication begins with the publication date. As this is linked to the assignment of a DOI, there is no end date. Instead, the data is stored for as long as storage space is available.
- **Contributors:** As a rule, the authors of the data publication are the contributors. However, other individuals who have contributed to the dataset may also be listed. A long-term contact person or responsible organization is designated for each dataset.
- **License information:** Each dataset is published in accordance with the FAIR principles under a clear and transparent license, thereby enabling third parties to reuse the data in a legally compliant manner.
- **(Re)use:** Published datasets are made publicly available for free download and reuse, provided that no necessary access restrictions or embargo periods have been set. Datasets published subject to access restrictions or embargoes may be requested through a transparent procedure in accordance with the FAIR principles. The metadata for published datasets is always publicly available under a CC0 license.

Enabling cooperative use

FDM:Storage.nrw is a cooperative information infrastructure⁹. The RDM State Basic Service must ensure that individuals who are primarily responsible for applying for and using storage space on FDM:Storage.nrw are employed by a participating institution or have a direct affiliation with an NFDI consortium based at a participating institution. A direct connection is deemed to exist if direct supervision by NFDI staff within the respective research initiative can be demonstrated.

RDM State Basic Services that allocate storage space on FDM:Storage.nrw must be open to all participating DH.NRW member universities. They may also be offered to other research institutions in North Rhine-Westphalia, subject to a contribution towards costs that cover the additional expenses incurred (staff costs for operation and service management). When applying for access to FDM:Storage.nrw, the RDM State Basic Services must demonstrate that they have qualified in accordance with the funding rules for DH.NRW projects¹⁰. In their public communications, they must clearly target user groups that extend beyond the local institution. An authentication method supported by IDM.NRW must be used.

Compliance with the FAIR principles

Research data stored on FDM:Storage.nrw must be stored in accordance with the FAIR principles, considering the specific use case and stage of the research data lifecycle. RDM State Basic Services ensure compliance with all elements of the FAIR principles, require their users to adhere to them, and review the relevant concepts as part of their award procedure. These criteria relate, amongst other things, to the allocation of PIDs per initiative and associated datasets (buckets),

⁹ See also DFG-Diskussionspapier „Digitale Forschungspraxis und kooperative Informationsinfrastrukturen“ (accessed on 07.05.2026)

¹⁰ See Förderung digitalisierungsbezogener Kooperationsvorhaben, DH.NRW, <https://www.dh.nrw/foerderung> (accessed on 07.05.2026)

the linking to a minimum set of metadata, and the facilitation of role structures. The minimum set of metadata per research initiative is as follows:

- Name of the initiative
- Description of the initiative (abstract)
- Name of the principal investigator(s) (PIs), including email address(es)
- Start
- End (for the definition, see the chapter on research initiatives)
- DFG discipline
- Responsible Organisation
- If applicable: Additional Organisation
- Keywords

The specific support provided by each access layer for the FAIR principles must be set out in a published document. Part of the development of the RDM State Basic Service must involve the regular identification and implementation of measures to improve the service in line with the FAIR principles.

Publication Selection Policy

Each RDM State Basic Service must publish a selection policy (outlining the selection criteria) setting out the guidelines for the allocation of storage space on FDM:Storage.nrw to end users.

Submission of reporting figures

Each RDM State Basic Service must provide a report on the allocation of storage space at least once a month, which must be publicly accessible to universities, broken down by DFG subject area and participating universities. This monthly reporting enables the FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management to monitor trends and developments in a timely manner and helps to identify deviations at an early stage and, where necessary, take measures, e.g. to procure new resources. To this end, all RDM State Basic Services record the relevant metrics at the level of individual research initiatives.

The purpose of the reporting is to provide transparency regarding the use of FDM:Storage.nrw. It aims to demonstrate how frequently and to what extent FDM:Storage.nrw is used, to highlight its importance for research at the participating universities. Furthermore, the reporting serves to provide decision-makers within the FDM:Storage.nrw governance structure (service management, advisory board, operating committee) with data that contributes to the improvement, targeted investment and further development of the infrastructure. DH.NRW and the MKW, as funding bodies, are also part of the target group.

The published data must be anonymized (no direct link to research initiatives or individuals involved should be identifiable) and must include the following information:

1. **Storage space used:** Amount of storage space currently used by the RDM State Basic Service.
2. **Storage space utilization:** Ratio of used to allocated storage space (as a percentage).
3. **Number of users:** How many users have an account with the service and how many of them actively use it.

4. **Average usage per organization:** Average storage usage per participating university.
5. **Data growth:** Rate at which the amount of used storage space has increased over the past week.
6. **Storage usage by category:** Breakdown of storage used by DFG subject area at the service and initiative levels.

The reporting figures must be made available for the Advisory Board's half-yearly meetings (held in January and June each year). A reminder will be sent out one month in advance by FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management.

Involvement of staff representatives

RDM State Basic Services wishing to access FDM:Storage.nrw must provide all necessary information to the relevant staff representative bodies at the participating universities. This usually includes clear documentation (e.g. authorization policies, guidelines on data deletion, data protection policies) to ensure compliance with legal and organizational requirements based on the State Staff Representation Act. This requirement can be met as part of the DH.NRW application process for the State Basic Service.

Publication of acknowledgements

Each RDM State Basic Service must state on its website that it uses storage space provided by FDM:Storage.nrw. This statement may be read as follows:

A key component of [RDM State Basic Service Name] is access for researchers to storage space within the DH.NRW research data infrastructure (FDM:Storage.nrw). FDM:Storage.nrw is funded by the Ministry of Culture and Science of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia (DataStorage.nrw: MKW: 214-76.01.09-7-7937; DataArchive.nrw: MKW: 76.04.10-06 – 2024-6188) and the German Research Foundation (DataStorage.nrw: DFG: INST 222/1530-1; DataArchive.nrw: DFG: INST 222/1581-1). The joint, distributed object storage system for central applications is managed by the FDM:Storage.nrw consortium. The participating universities are RWTH Aachen University as consortium leader, as well as Aachen University of Applied Sciences, Ruhr University Bochum, TU Dortmund University, University of Duisburg-Essen, University of Cologne and University of Paderborn.

Researchers using FDM:Storage.nrw should be asked to include the following acknowledgement in their publications and conference proceedings:

If you publish your research (meta)data via [RDM State Basic Service Name] and, in connection with this, produce a publication, we would be grateful if you could mention this in your acknowledgements. Please simply use the following citation template:

The data used in this publication is managed via [Service Name], whose storage space forms part of FDM:Storage.nrw. FDM:Storage.nrw is funded by the Ministry of Culture and Science of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia (DataStorage.nrw: MKW: 214-76.01.09-7-7937; DataArchive.nrw: MKW: 76.04.10-06 – 2024-6188) and the German Research Foundation (DataStorage.nrw: DFG: INST 222/1530-1; DataArchive.nrw: DFG: INST 222/1581-1).

Accreditation of RDM State Basic Services

RDM State Basic Services that allocate storage space on FDM:Storage.nrw are accredited by FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management on the recommendation of the Advisory Board. Accreditation is valid indefinitely, provided that the criteria set out in this distribution concept are met. However, FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management or the advisory board may, where there is a legitimate interest, arrange for an audit of the RDM State Basic Services to review the accreditation. An unsuccessful audit may, because of the FDM:Storage.nrw decision-making process, lead to conditions being imposed on the continued provision of the RDM State Basic Service or to the immediate withdrawal of accreditation by FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management.

Compliance with the distribution concept is monitored and ensured by the FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management. Should RDM State Basic Services wish to access FDM:Storage.nrw, the advisory board must issue a recommendation to that effect. The advisory board thus advises the FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management at RWTH Aachen University in its role as the lead institution of the consortium, which makes the final decision.

The following additional documents are required for accreditation:

- Concept description (RDM State Basic Service and assessment procedure)
- Mission Statement
- Selection Criteria (Selection Policy)
- Explanation of the FAIR Principles
- LOIs of universities in the DH.NRW funding application
- Staff council vote

Once accreditation has been successfully completed, the FDM:Storage.nrw Service Management will inform the FDM:Storage.nrw Operating Committee about the new RDM State Basic Service.

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We would like to thank the advisory board of FDM:Storage.nrw and the Operating Committee for their support in drawing up this distribution concept. FDM:Storage.nrw is funded by the Ministry of Culture and Science of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia (DataStorage.nrw: MKW: 214-76.01.09-7-7937; DataArchive.nrw: MKW: 76.04.10-06 – 2024-6188) and the German Research Foundation (DataStorage.nrw: DFG: INST 222/1530-1; DataArchive.nrw: DFG: INST 222/1581-1). The shared, distributed object storage system for central applications is managed by the FDM:Storage.nrw consortium. The participating universities are RWTH Aachen University as consortium leader, as well as Aachen University of Applied Sciences, Ruhr University Bochum, TU Dortmund, University of Duisburg-Essen, University of Cologne and University of Paderborn.